

Information Literacy Variables and Medical Students' Utilization of Information Resources in Federal University Libraries in South - South, Nigeria

Aniebiet Inyang Ntui
Department of Library and Information Science
University of Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria
ntuinju@gmail.com

Affiong Emmanuel Effiong
Medical library, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
ellalove668@gmail.com

Eseme Augustine Jonah
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
esemejonah@gmail.com

Paper Type: Empirical research

Background: The primary purpose of the university library is to support the objectives of the parent institution. The objectives are to encourage and promote teaching, learning and research in a consistent manner. Libraries like other organizations are a part of larger social systems which have been created to conserve knowledge, preserve the cultural heritage and provide information (ALA, 2000). University libraries are meant to serve students, lecturers and other members of the university community. The basic and the most essential function of the libraries is to ensure maximum utilization of the accumulated recorded knowledge and information. The transmission of knowledge and information is, therefore, the fundamental task of libraries. According to Whittaker (1993), Information explosion has informed modern societies of the growing importance of special knowledge in accessing and utilizing information from different sources and formats. There is a growing need for people to acquire new skills of accessing information resources in new formats and such skills are acquired through information literacy. Information literacy lies at the heart of lifelong learning, it enables the students to take control of their information needs and become more independent, assuring personal control of their learning and becoming aware of effective processes for finding, analyzing and using information (Vasuderan, 2014). The study determined the influence of information literacy variables such as ability to use information access tools, ability to evaluate information resources and user education on medical students' utilization of information resources in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Research questions: Research questions raised to guide the study were: (a) to what extent does the ability to use information access tools influence medical students' utilization of library information resources?; (b) how does the ability to evaluate information influence medical students' utilization of library information resources?; and (c) to what extent does user education influence medical students' utilization of library resources

Purpose: The study was undertaken to determine how information literacy variables influence utilization of library information resources among medical students' in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. Specifically, to determine how the ability to use information

access tools and the ability to evaluate information influence medical students' utilization of library information resources.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: the study adopted survey research design. The population of this study comprised of 1,141 medical students from the 4 universities namely: University of Port-Harcourt, University of Uyo, University of Calabar and University of Benin. Stratified random sampling and purposive sampling technique were used to select a sample of 456 from 1,141 population of medical students from universities under study representing 40% of the population. A well-structured and validated questionnaire "Information Literacy Variables and Medical Students Utilization of Library Resources (ILVMSULIRQ)" was the instrument used for data collection. A reliability test was conducted using Cronbach Alpha method and the reliability coefficient ranged from 0.71 to 0.87 after conducting a trial test outside the study area. Data were analyzed using simple regression analysis. All the hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

Findings: There was a significant influence of ability to use access tools and user education on medical students' utilization of information resources. On the other hand, ability to evaluate information did not have significant influence on medical students' utilization of library information resources.

Originality/Value: Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that National University Commission should separate the use of library as a course from the use of English so that adequate credit hours can be allocated for the use of library and this would enhance acquisition of information literacy skills thereby increasing accessibility and utilization of library information resources. Also, user education programs should be organized regularly by library management and staff for students to ensure their independence in information search and retrieval and to become lifelong learners.

Keywords: Information literacy, Utilization, Medical students, Federal University, Libraries.

References

- American Library Association ALA (2000). *Information literacy competency standards for higher education*. Available at www.ala.org accessed 3rd July, 2018.
- Popoola, S.O. & Haliso, Y. (2009). Use of library information resources services as predictor of the teaching effectiveness of social scientist in Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Library, Archival and Information Science*, 19(1), 65 - 77.
- UNESCO (2008). *Developing countries and information science and the national forum of information literacy for use at the information literacy meeting of experts*. Available at <http://www.nelis.gov/lib>. Accessed July, 6th 2018.
- Vasudevan, T.M. (2012). Information literacy of research scholars of universities in Kerala. (An unpublished doctoral thesis). University of Calicut. Retrieved from <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/robs>
- Whittaker, R. (1993). *Challenges in information technology management in the 21st century*. Retrieved on November 10, 2018. Accessed @ <https://www.googlebook.com>